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Performance of Milk Production in Smallholders: A case Study of Cu Chi District, Ho Chi Minh City of Vietnam

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ABSTRACT

Cu Chi is a suburban district in Ho Chi Minh City in Vietnam with 66,700 dairy cows, and produce more than 400 tons milk daily. Dairy farming creates stable jobs and brings high economic efficiency to nearly 8,300 dairy farmers and thousands of other farmers in this region. This research based on the surveyed data from 40 dairy farmers in the study sites in the first quarter of 2017 by semi-structure, standard questionnaires and PRA method to find out the real situation of performance of dairy milk production in the region and suggest some recommendations for the dairy farming development in other regions in Vietnam. The findings showed that milk yield in this region was not high, but due to low purchased feed cost with the using of family labor led to low production cost, the farm margin was quite high, accounted for 57.7% milk receipts. Some recommendations for dairy farmers in other regions of Vietnam: Farmers had better use family labors; use by-products to feed their cows, well manage the cost of production, especially, reduce the purchased feed cost, improve milk quality and consider to the efficiency and sustainability of the farms.

Keywords: dairy, milk production, performance, receipts.

1. INTRODUCTION

Vietnam has a tropical monsoon climate with an average relative humidity of 84–100%. Vietnam also suffers from many natural disasters such as storms, flooding, drought, etc., often following an annual cyclical pattern. Natural conditions do not weigh in favor of the dairy industry (Bui Thi Nga, 2014). However, in the recent years, thanks to the increasing in living standard, with the conditions of the international economic integration, dairy become one of the important industry in Vietnam.

Cu Chi is a suburban district and the key district in dairy husbandry in Ho Chi Minh City¹ in Vietnam. Cu Chi has a large land area, facilitating to the grass for the dairy cows. It has a total herd of 66,700 dairy cows (in October 2016), accounting for 2/3 of the total head cows of Ho Chi Minh city (Thanh Nguyen, 2016). The farmers in this district produce more than 400 tons milk daily. Dairy farming creates stable jobs and brings high economic efficiency to nearly 8,300 farmers in 20 communes and towns of the Cu Chi district. It also creates stable jobs and incomes for thousands of other farmers who grow grass for sale for dairy farmers in this region. This research is done to find out the real situation of performance of dairy milk production in the region and suggest some recommendations for the dairy farming development in other regions in Vietnam.

2. METHODOLOGY

The Cu Chi district was chosen as a study site because: (i) this region is located in the Southern area and have the highest numbers of dairy head in Ho Chi Minh City; (ii) farmers in this region have a long time experience in dairy milk production compared to other regions; (iii) dairy is the key economic activities in this region.

The primary data came from a survey of 40 dairy farms in the study sites in the first quarter of 2017 based on semi-structured, standard questionnaires and PRA method.

¹ The largest city of Vietnam

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Major resources of milk production

- Labor

For dairy farming, labor plays an important role as dairy cows are quite sensitive and require careful, continuous care. In the study area, family labor was used mainly for dairy farming, at an average of 2 laborers per household. The maximum number of family workers is only four. There were 28 out of 40 (70%) households hiring more labor in the labor market with a few numbers (1 to 4 people), mainly for seasonal or crop jobs, eg. grass cutting. This number is lower than our previous studies in some Northern regions of Vietnam (Bui Thi Nga, Philippe Lebailly, Tran Huu Cuong, 2011; Bui Thi Nga, Luong Thu Ha, 2016; Bui Thi Nga, 2017).

Table 1: Labors condition

Unit: Person

Detail	n	Mean (SD)	Median (Min; Max)
Hired labor	28	0.29 (0.85)	0 (0; 3)
Wage for hired labor	2	4250 (1767.77)	4250 (3000; 5500)
Hired female labor	23	0 (0)	0 (0; 0)
Family labors	38	2.18 (0.8)	2 (1; 4)
Female family labors	34	0.85 (0.5)	1 (0; 2)

Source: Survey results, 2017

- Land

Similarly, land plays an important role in growing forage for dairy cattle. The survey showed that the area of agricultural land in this region is limited. The average land area per farm was 9701 square meters (m²), of which land for grass growing accounted for 95%. The average land area per head cow was 409 m² and the acreage of grass growing per head was 389 m². According to respondents, this area was not enough for them to grow grass for cattle. They have to buy more grass from outside, pushed up the cost of raising livestock, and reduced their profits. There were 50% of households needed more land for grass growing with a minimum area of 100 m², and maximum area of 20,000 m². This land area was also lower than those in some other regions of our previous studies and in the Northern area of Vietnam (Bui Thi Nga, Philippe Lebailly, Tran Huu Cuong, 2011; Bui Thi Nga, Luong Thu Ha, 2016; Bui Thi Nga, Tran Huu Cuong, Do Thi My Hanh, 2017).

Table 2: Land condition

Unit: m²

Detail	n	Mean (SD)	Median (Min; Max)
Agriculture land	35	9701.51 (17504.32)	3300 (50; 90200)
Agricultural land/head		409.3249	
Forage area	37	9222.43 (17108.28)	3000 (0; 90000)
Forage area/head		389.1321	
Heifers' stall area	37	334.95 (504.66)	200 (28; 3000)
Land for other kind of husbandry	26	19.23 (49.15)	0 (0; 200)
Perennial tree land	26	85 (392.54)	0 (0; 2000)
Food crop and vegetable land	24	64.58 (276.81)	0 (0; 1350)
Garden	36	880.19 (3150.04)	155 (40; 19000)
Total square	34	10868.62 (19159.43)	4420 (208; 90350)
More needed area	20	2597.5 (4772.63)	500 (100; 20000)

Source: Survey results, 2017

- Herd size

The average size of the herd in the study site was approximately 24 heads per farm. The minimum farms had 7 cows and the maximum had 60 cows. Quite different from our previous studies in some region in the Northern areas of Vietnam, such as Son La, Tuyen Quang, Ha Nam, Hanoi, (Bui Thi Nga, Philippe Lebailly, Tran Huu Cuong, 2012, Bui Thi Nga, 2014), many farms in this region raised both dairy cows and beefs with an average number of four to five. There were some farms raised around 30 beefs.

Table 3: Herd size

Unit: head

Detail	n	Mean (SD)	Median (Min; Max)
Total cattle	40	23.7 (12.7)	22.5 (7; 60)
Beef and male calves	40	4.4 (5.2)	3.5 (0; 30)
Dairy cattle	40	19.3 (10.93)	16 (6; 56)
Calves and heifers	40	8.43 (5.8)	7 (1; 26)
Calves on milk	40	3.3 (3.63)	2 (0; 13)
Weaned calves (Weaned to one year)	39	2.15 (2.5)	1 (0; 12)
Heifers (From 1 year to first pregnancy)	40	3.02 (3.64)	2 (0; 13)
Weaned calves and heifers (weaned to first pregnancies)	40	5.12 (3.8)	4 (0; 14)

Source: Survey results, 2017

The average dairy cattle in the region were 19 heads, and the median was 16 heads. Of which, 44.6% were calves and heifers, the rest were lactating and dry cows.

3.2 Milk production

- Milking time

Farmers milked twice a day. The average milking time was 53 minutes for the entire lactating cows and the average for the transport of the milk from the producer to the collector was 16 minutes. Thus, it takes 79 minutes from the beginning of milking to deliver. This is quite long and will likely reduce milk quality as milk is fresh, easily damaged food even under normal temperature conditions.

Table 4: Milking time

Detail	Unit	n	Mean (SD)	Median (Min; Max)
Milking times per day	Times	40	2 (0)	2 (2; 2)
Milking duration of whole herd (from the first cow to the last cow)	Minute	39	52.95 (27.43)	50 (15; 120)
Milk-transporting duration (from finish milking until finish delivery milk)	Minute	39	15.97 (11.96)	15 (3; 60)

Source: Survey results, 2017

- Milk yield

The average lactation number of surveyed cows in this region was nearly 3 with the maximum of 9 litters. This number is similar to the average number in Ha Nam province, but lower than that in Son la province (Bui Thi Nga, 2014; Nguyen Ngoc Thien, 2010; Bui Thi Nga, 2017). The average lactation milk yield per cow was quite low at only 3,945.4 kilograms (kg), the lowest milk yield was only 2400 kg and the maximum was 6000 kg.

Table 5: Milk yield

Detail	Unit	n	Mean (SD)	Median (Min; Max)
Average lactation number	Litters	34	2.97 (1.38)	2.5 (1; 8.5)
Estimated average lactation milk yield per cow	Kg	37	3945.41 (780.58)	4000 (2400; 6000)
Milk Yield 1 (Farmer answered, Kg/cow/day)	Kg/cow/day	40	13.88 (4.01)	14.88 (0; 19.5)
Milk Yield 2 (Calculation, Kg/cow/day)	Kg/cow/day	39	15.22 (2.54)	15 (10; 20)
Milk fat	%	39	3.62 (0.4)	3.5
Milk protein	%	23	2.85 (0.4)	2.8 (1.7; 4)
SNF	%	30	8.41 (0.39)	8.5 (7.1; 9)

Source: Survey results, 2017

The average milk yield per day per cow in this region was rather low at only 15.22 kg. Interestingly, this calculation number was even higher than the number according to farmers' answer (13.88kg). This can be explained by the fact that the farmers did not record the information and data in farms so normally they underestimated their milk yield.

Almost farmers knew and remembered their milk fat and it was quite high at an average of 3.62%, with the median of 3.5%. However, only 57.5% farmers remembered their milk protein and the average numbers was 2.85% of the median of 2.8%. Of the 75% farmers remembered the SNF, the average number was 8.41% and median of 8.5%.

3.3 Farm receipts

In this region, farmers received average of 58.7 million Vietnam dong (VND²) per cow per year or 645.5 million VND per farm annually. They got receipts of 12,532.7 VND per kg of milk, mainly from milk, which occupied 93.7% total receipts. Non milk receipts accounted for only 6.3%, of which, stock sales of dairy were only 1.1% because farmers often kept their cows until they could not keep it for some reasons such as too old or unproductive cows or death. It seems that the farmers do not think much about a replacement for their herd improvement.

Table 6: Cash receipts

CASH RECEIPTS	VND/kg	VND/cow	% Farm receipts	Total Earned
Milk Receipts	11738.3	54,962,227	93.7	604.584.500
Stock sales - dairy	142.7	668,182	1.1	7.350.000
Stock sales - other	383.4	1,795,114	3.1	19.746.250
Other receipts	268.4	1,256,533	2.1	13.821.857
Non milk receipts	794.4	3,719,828	6.3	40.918.107
Total Farm Receipts	12532.7	58,682,055	100.0	645.502.607

Source: Survey results, 2017

3.4 Cost of production

Almost farmers fed their cow with purchase concentrated feed, purchase rice straw and their homegrown king grass. The total purchased feed was nearly 5,000 VND per kg of milk, which accounted for 42.3% total milk receipts. This number is lower than those in our other previous researches (Bui Thi Nga, 2017; Bui Thi Nga, 2014; Bui Thi Nga, Philippe Lebaillly, Tran Huu Cuong, 2011). In my opinion, this is good for farmers as they could reduce the proportion of purchasing feed cost, which in turn, will increase their profitability.

² VND is Vietnam currency. 1 USD= 22,700 VND by 23/7/2017, source: formal exchange rate of Vietnam at <https://www.vietcombank.com.vn/exchangerates/>

Table 7: Cost of production

PRODUCTION COSTS	VND/Kg	VND/cow	% Milk receipts	Total Spent
Purchased feed	4960.1	23,224,629	42.3	255,470,916
Fertilizer	46.6	218,182	0.4	2,400,000
Fuel & Oil	19.4	90,909	0.2	1,000,000
Seed	9.7	45,455	0.1	500,000
Irrigation costs	0.0	0,0	0.0	0
Repairs & Maintenance	97.1	454,546	0.8	5,000,000
Other feed costs	9.7	45,456	0.1	500,000
Feed Related costs	5142.6	24,079,174	43.8	264,870,916
Animal Health	46.6	218,182	0.4	2,400,000
Herd Improvement	112.1	524,727	1.0	5,772,000
Herd Costs	158.7	742,909	1.4	8,172,000
Dairy Shed Costs - Electricity	293.3	1,373,456	2.5	15,108,000
Dairy Shed Costs - Chemicals	60.7	283,986	0.5	3,123,840
Shed Costs	354.0	1,657,440	3.0	18,231,840
Cartage	9.7	45,454	0.1	500,000
Levies	0.0	0,0	0.0	0
Sundry Variable Costs (miscellaneous)	97.1	454,546	0.8	5,000,000
Other variable costs	106.8	500,000	0.9	5,500,000
Total Variable Costs	5762.0	26,979,523	49.1	296,774,756

Source: Survey results, 2017

Feed related costs in this region accounted for 43.8% total milk receipts. Herd cost and shed cost accounted for 1.4% and 3.0% milk receipts, respectively. Totally, the variable cost of milk production accounted for only 49.1% total milk receipts.

3.5 Farm gross margin

Due to a quite lower proportion of production cost, margin over feed related costs in this region was 56.2%. The average milk gross margin calculated per kg milk was 5,976 VND, accounted for 50.9%, and farm gross margin calculated per kg milk was 6,770.7 VND, occupied 57.7%. These numbers were much higher than those in some other regions of our previous researches (Bui Thi Nga, Philippe Lebailly, Tran Huu Cuong, 2011; Bui Thi Nga, Tran Huu Cuong, Do Thi My Hanh, 2017).

Table 8: Farm gross margin

Detail	VND/kg	VND/cow	% Milk receipts	Total per farm
Milk Receipts	11738.3	54,962,227	100	604,584,500
Non milk receipts	794.4	3,719,828		40,918,107
<i>Total Farm Receipts</i>	<i>12532.7</i>	<i>58,682,055</i>		<i>645,502,607</i>
Feed Related costs	5142.6	24,079,174	43.8	264,870,916
Margin over feed related costs	6595.7	30,883,053	56.2	339,713,584
<i>Total Variable Costs</i>	<i>5762.0</i>	<i>26,979,523</i>	<i>49.1</i>	<i>296,774,756</i>
<i>Gross Margin - milk only</i>	<i>5976.3</i>	<i>27,982,704</i>	<i>50.9</i>	<i>307,809,744</i>
<i>Gross Margin - whole farm</i>	<i>6770.7</i>	<i>31,702,532</i>	<i>57.7</i>	<i>348,727,851</i>

Source: Survey results, 2017

3.6 Some affecting factors to performance of milk production

- Age of farm owners

The average age of dairy farm owners in the study site was high, at 46 years old. The youngest was 29 years old and the eldest was 62 years old. At this age, farmers have accumulated capital, experience to develop their livestock. However, this age was quite old to adopt new knowledge, technology, skills or technique of production.

- Climate

The Cu Chi district has geographic coordinates from 10°53'00" to 10°10'00" North latitude and 106°22'00" to 106°40'00" East longitude, lying in the tropics with monsoon climate. The climate is divided into two distinct seasons, rainy season from May to November, dry season from December to April. The difference between day and night temperature is quite large, in the dry season is 8 – 10°C. Average humidity in the air is 79.5%, highest in July and August at 80-90%, lowest in December at 70.1%. The weather conditions are so hot and humid that it is not favorable for the development of dairy farming.

- Educational level

There were 30.8% of 39 respondents with the highest educational level of elementary only. There were only 2 respondents (5.1%) with the highest educational level of college. These numbers showed that the educational level of the surveyed farmers was quite low. With a low education level, the ability to acquire scientific knowledge, technology and technological innovation is low.

Figure 1. Educational level
Source: Survey results, 2017

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In the study site, family labor was mainly used for dairy farming, at an average of 2 laborers per household. Land area for dairy husbandry was low, at an average of 389 m² per head for the grass growing, thus, many farmers have to buy more grass from outside for their herd. The average size of the herd in the study site was approximately 24 heads per farm, of which, the dairy herd was 19 heads and beef was nearly 5 heads.

The time from the beginning of milking to delivery (79 minutes) was quite long and would reduce milk quality as milk is fresh, easily damaged food. The average milk yield per day per cow in this region was rather low at only 15.22 kg and the average lactation milk yield per cow was quite low at only 3,945.4 kg with the milk fat of 3.62%, milk protein of 2.85%, and SNF was 8.41%.

The farmers received quite high on average of 58.7 million VND per cow per year or 645.5 million VND per farm annually. They got receipts of 12,532.7 VND per kg of milk, of which 93.7% from milk. The purchased feed cost was around 5,000 VND per kg of milk production, accounting for 42.3% milk receipts, feed related costs in this region accounted for 43.8% total milk receipts. Herd cost and shed cost accounted for 1.4 and 3.0% milk receipts, respectively. Hence, total variable cost of milk production accounted for only 49.1% total milk receipts. Even they got a lower milk yield, but with low cost of production, and low cost of labor due to using family labor, led to quite a high margin over feed related costs in this region were 56.2%. The average milk gross margin calculated per kg milk was 5,976 VND, accounted for 50.9%, and farm gross margin calculated per kg milk was 6,770.7 VND, occupied 57.7%.

Some affecting factors to performance of milk production in this region was quite a high age with low educational level of farm owners, which could reduce the ability of adapting the new knowledge, technique of production; quite hot and humid climate condition was not favorable for the development of dairy farming. These factors might have a negative impact on the performance of milk production in the region.

From the real situation of performance of milk production in the study site, some recommendations for dairy farmers in other regions of Vietnam are:

- Farmers had better use their family labor to reduce the labor cost, which, in turn, reduce the production cost and improve the farm performance.
- Farmers should use by-products to feed their cows, well manage their cost of production, especially, reduce the purchased feed cost to enhance their performance.
- They also could increase their performance by improving their milk quality because when milk quality increase, milk price will go up and milk receipts will rise.
- In this region, even the milk yield was quite low, the performance was quite good with high gross margin. Therefore, farmers should not concentrate to increase the milk yield by all means, but they should consider to the efficiency and sustainability of the farms.

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